

Effect of Different Solvent Characteristics on the Proton Ligand and Cu^{2+} Ligand Equilibrium and Formation Constants of N-Benzoyl Phenyl Hydroxyl Amine in Various Mixed Aqueous Solvents

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Complex equilibria of N-Benzoyl phenyl hydroxyl amine (NBPHA) with proton and Cu^{2+} ion have been measured in various mixed aqueous solvents viz. dioxane-water, isopropanol-water, acetone-water, ethanol-water and methanol-water. ${}^P K_1^H$ of NBPHA and equilibrium constant $\beta = \frac{[\text{CuL}][\text{H}]}{[\text{Cu}][\text{HL}]}$ and formation constant $\beta' = \frac{[\text{CuL}]}{[\text{Cu}][\text{L}]}$ were also measured in each of the solvents varying their proportions with water in a range where the complex remains soluble. The variance of $\log {}^P K_1^H$, $\log \beta$ and $\log \beta'$ with the inverse of dielectric constant or mole fraction of the solvent has been studied. $\log {}^P K_1^H$ generally varies linearly with $1/\epsilon$ or mole fraction. $\log \beta$ increases with decrease of dielectric constant or with increase of the mole fraction of the organic solvent. $\log \beta'$ also increases with the decrease of dielectric constant and increase of mole fraction. Here in many cases the variation is linear. Linearity of these curves and deviations from linearity are explained by solvent effects. The effects of solvent on the values of the constants are discussed and explained in the light of three effects, (1) change of H-bonding in water on introduction of organic solvent, (2) proton solvation of the organic solvent, (3) change of dielectric constant of water by mixing with organic solvents.

Application of Fuoss expression and consideration of both electrostatic and non-electrostatic effects were made to explain the values of the constants.

A number of studies¹⁻⁹ have been made on the dependence of proton ligand and metal ligand formation constants of complexes on properties of solvents. In the studies of complex equilibria in different mixed aqueous solvents, the organic solvents certainly play an important role. On introduction of an organic solvent in water the solvent characteristics gradually undergo change. Thus lattice structure of water is gradually broken down¹⁰ and the solvent becomes more proton solvating. At high concentration of the organic solvent the latter solvates protons¹¹. Over and above this the dielectric constant of the medium changes and this has a very important role. Rorabacher *et al.*¹ used Fuoss expression^{1,2} for ion-pair equilibrium constant to explain protonation constants of acetates, polyaminocarboxylates etc. in methanol water system. Bates *et al.*^{1,3} and Rorabacher *et al.*¹ have stressed upon both electrostatic and nonelectrostatic effects on the proton ligand formation constant. Gergely and Kiss⁴ have studied the formation constants of proton, copper and nickel complexes of alanine in dioxane water and methanol water. They found gradual deviation from linearity when $\log K$ is plotted against inverse of dielectric constant.

In the present paper complex equilibria of Cu^{2+} ion and NBPHA ligand were measured in various mixed aqueous solvents containing dioxane, isopropanol, acetone, ethanol and methanol. Detailed studies were

made by varying the proportion of each mixed aqueous solvent. Explanation for the sequence of values of $\log {}^P K_1^H$, equilibrium constant ($\log \beta$) and formation constant ($\log \beta'$) are given with the help of solvent effects. The variations of $\log {}^P K_1^H$ of NBPHA and $\log \beta$ and $\log \beta'$ of the complex with change of dielectric constant or mole fraction are measured. These were also explained by considering the solvent effects.

Experimental

All reagents were of AR or GR grade. The titrations were carried out in 50%, 60%, 75% and 85% (v/v) dioxane-water; 60%, 75%, 80% and 85% (v/v) isopropanol-water; 70%, 75%, 80% and 85% (v/v) acetone-water; 70%, 75%, 80% and 85% (v/v) ethanol-water and 70%, 75%, 80% and 85% (v/v) methanol-water medium at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The lowest limits of the volume proportions were restricted by the solubility of the complex. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1M NaClO_4 . The pH measurements were made with a bench model Cambridge pH meter using glass electrodes as usual. The composition of the experimental solutions and measurement of [H] are described in a previous paper⁹.

As the reaction takes the course⁹

equilibrium constants are calculated by the method for monoprotic ligands¹⁴. Free ligand concentration is measured by the expression

$$[\text{HL}] = (T_{\text{HL}}^0 - \bar{n} T_M^0) \frac{V^0}{(V^0 + V'')}$$

The equilibrium constants

$$\beta_1 = \frac{[\text{CuL}][\text{H}]}{[\text{Cu}][\text{HL}]} \text{ and } \beta_2 = \frac{[\text{CuL}_2][\text{H}]^2}{[\text{Cu}][\text{HL}]^2}$$

were calculated by the expression

$$\sum_{n=0}^{n=\bar{n}} (\bar{n} - n) \beta_n \frac{[\text{HL}]^n}{[\text{H}]^n} = 0$$

$$\frac{\bar{n} [\text{H}]}{(\bar{n} - 1) [\text{HL}]} (-Y) \text{ was plotted vs } \frac{(2 - \bar{n}) [\text{HL}]}{(\bar{n} - 1) [\text{H}]} (-X)$$

in large graph papers and points falling on approximate straight line are used for calculation. The constants were computed by Burroughs 6700 system. Here essentially the standard least square technique is adopted. But it is so programmed that several least square values of constants are obtained by considering several sets of experimental points. Finally the mean of the several values was found out and standard deviation calculated.

The values of ${}^P K_1^H$ were measured with the help of expression $\log {}^P K_1^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A}$ and using usual procedure.

The formation constants β_1' and β_2' were also calculated by the relation

$$\beta_1 = \frac{[\text{CuL}]}{[\text{Cu}][\text{L}]} \frac{[\text{H}][\text{L}]}{[\text{HL}]}$$

$$\log \beta_1 = \log \beta_1' - \log {}^P K_1^H \text{ and } \log \beta_2 = \log \beta_2' - 2 \log {}^P K_1^H$$

Results and Discussion

The values of $\log {}^P K_1^H$, $\log \beta_1$, $\log \beta_2$, $\log \beta_1'$ and $\log \beta_2'$ of the complexes and $1/\epsilon$ values of the solvents are shown in Table 1. From the data (Table 1) it can be shown that $\log {}^P K_1^H$ increases with the increase in the percentage of organic solvent of the media. Fig. 1 shows that the plot of $\log {}^P K_1^H$ against $1/\epsilon$ is always linear except in case of dioxane water mixture. Fig. 3 illustrates the linear dependence of $\log {}^P K_1^H$ on the mole fraction of all solvent mixtures except dioxane water which shows slight deviation. For a particular composition of solvent water mixture (say 75% v/v) $1/\epsilon$ changes in the following order

Dioxane-water > Isoproponal-water > Acetone-water > Ethanol-water > Methanol-water

But for the same v/v composition $\log {}^P K_1^H$ in different solvent water mixtures follows the sequence

Acetone-water > Dioxane-water > Isoproponal-water > Ethanol-water > Methanol-water.

This indicates that the sequence does not follow the order of dielectric constants of the media. It is found that acetone which should have been in the third place has come up to the top.

In a mixed aqueous solvent the proton ligand formation constant may be influenced by different solvent characteristics. Three effects can be envisaged, (1) Dielectric constant of the mixed solvent, (2) Decrease in hydrogen bonding in water by the organic solvent and (3) Protonation of the organic solvent.

(1) Bates *et al.*¹³ and Rorabacher *et al.*¹ explained the change of $\log K^H$ with solvent composition considering both electrostatic and the nonelectrostatic effects. They concluded that the nonelectrostatic phenomenon becomes increasingly important in solvents containing greater than 50% methanol.

Protonation is viewed¹ as a two step process,

Solvent separated ion pair

$$\text{where } K_H = K_{os} \cdot K_{H-L} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The values of K_{os} , representing the diffusion controlled equilibrium constant for ion pair formation, can be calculated from Fuoss equation¹².

$$K_{os} = \frac{4}{3} \pi a^3 N_A 10^{-3} e^{-\frac{(Z_H Z_L e^2)}{\epsilon a k T}} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where a = centre to centre distance of closest approach between the solvated proton and base in the ion pair preceding the proton jump. Other terms have usual significance.

The term K_{H-L} in equation (2) represents the proton jump equilibrium occurring within the ion pair presumably a nonelectrostatic term, dependent primarily on the relative basicity of the solvent and the base with a contribution from the nature and orientation of the solvent molecules separating the solvated proton and base species in the ion pair. It also appears that nonelectrostatic part of the interaction is related to proton acceptance property of the medium and proton solvation of the organic solvent discussed below.

Taking logarithm on the expression (2) with inclusion of the Fuoss expression for K_{os} (3), we have,

TABLE I—EQUILIBRIUM DONSTANTS, FORMATION CONSTANTS AND PK_H^H VALUES OF Cu^{2+} AND PROTON COMPLEXES OF NBPHA IN MIXED AQUEOUS SOLVENTS AT $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ AND 0.1 M $NaClO_4$ IONIC STRENGTH.

Solvent Composition (%) v/v	Moler fraction	Reciprocal of D.C. (1/ε)	Log of equilibrium constant		log PK_H^H	Log of formation constants	
			log k_1	log β_n		log k'_1	log β'_n
Dioxane-water							
85	0.545	0.1220	$\bar{1}.49 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.54 \pm 0.01$	10.86 ± 0.02	10.35 ± 0.03	20.26 ± 0.05
75	0.388	0.0699	$\bar{1}.74 \pm 0.004$	$\bar{2}.42 \pm 0.004$	10.59 ± 0.01	10.33 ± 0.014	19.60 ± 0.024
60	0.240	0.0388	$\bar{1}.69 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.30 \pm 0.01$	10.34 ± 0.02	10.03 ± 0.03	18.98 ± 0.05
50	0.174	0.0293	$\bar{1}.68 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.25 \pm 0.01$	10.10 ± 0.01	9.78 ± 0.02	18.45 ± 0.03
Isopropanol-water							
85	0.572	0.0445	$\bar{1}.72 \pm 0.005$	$\bar{2}.78 \pm 0.01$	10.14 ± 0.02	9.86 ± 0.025	19.06 ± 0.05
80	0.486	0.0400	$\bar{1}.93 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.76 \pm 0.01$	9.94 ± 0.02	9.87 ± 0.03	18.64 ± 0.05
75	0.415	0.0359	$\bar{1}.92 \pm 0.02$	$\bar{2}.56 \pm 0.01$	9.83 ± 0.01	9.75 ± 0.03	18.22 ± 0.03
60	0.262	0.0260	$\bar{1}.88 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.10 \pm 0.01$	9.54 ± 0.01	9.42 ± 0.02	17.38 ± 0.03
Acetone-water							
85	0.579	0.0360	$\bar{1}.47 \pm 0.02$	$\bar{2}.36 \pm 0.01$	11.03 ± 0.02	10.50 ± 0.04	20.42 ± 0.05
80	0.495	0.0320	$\bar{1}.73 \pm 0.03$	$\bar{2}.16 \pm 0.02$	10.88 ± 0.02	10.61 ± 0.05	19.92 ± 0.06
75	0.422	0.0290	$\bar{1}.57 \pm 0.03$	$\bar{2}.00 \pm 0.02$	10.67 ± 0.01	10.24 ± 0.04	19.34 ± 0.04
70	0.365	0.0264	$\bar{1}.32 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{3}.62 \pm 0.005$	10.59 ± 0.01	9.91 ± 0.02	18.80 ± 0.025
Ethanol-water							
85	0.635	0.0322	$\bar{1}.82 \pm 0.02$	$\bar{2}.54 \pm 0.01$	10.04 ± 0.02	9.86 ± 0.04	18.62 ± 0.05
80	0.552	0.0294	$\bar{1}.83 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.66 \pm 0.004$	9.86 ± 0.01	9.69 ± 0.02	18.38 ± 0.024
75	0.479	0.0272	$\bar{1}.73 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.54 \pm 0.01$	9.74 ± 0.01	9.47 ± 0.02	18.02 ± 0.03
70	0.420	0.0251	$\bar{1}.72 \pm 0.01$	$\bar{2}.22 \pm 0.004$	9.64 ± 0.01	9.36 ± 0.02	17.50 ± 0.024
Methanol-water							
85	0.717	0.0262	$\bar{1}.82 \pm 0.02$	$\bar{2}.45 \pm 0.01$	9.72 ± 0.02	9.54 ± 0.04	17.89 ± 0.05
80	0.614	0.0245	$\bar{1}.75 \pm 0.02$	$\bar{2}.48 \pm 0.02$	9.63 ± 0.01	9.38 ± 0.03	17.74 ± 0.04
75	0.573	0.0230	$\bar{1}.73 \pm 0.02$	$\bar{2}.38 \pm 0.01$	9.57 ± 0.01	9.30 ± 0.03	17.52 ± 0.03
70	0.510	0.0217	$\bar{1}.59 \pm 0.02$	$\bar{2}.23 \pm 0.01$	9.46 ± 0.01	9.05 ± 0.03	17.15 ± 0.03

Fig. 1. Variation of $\log PK_H^H$ vs $1/\epsilon$ in various mixed aqueous solvents. The lower scale ($1/\epsilon$) is for dioxane-water.
 1. Dioxane-water; 2. Isopropanol-water; 3. Acetone-water; 4. Ethanol-water and 5. Methanol-water

$$\log K_H = \log \frac{4}{3} \pi N_A 10^{-3} + 3 \log a + \log K_{H-L}$$

$$- \frac{Z_H Z_L e_0^2}{2.303 k T a} \cdot 1/\epsilon \quad \dots (4)$$

Putting the value of Z_L ($= -1$) it is understood that with decreasing dielectric constant (ϵ) of the medium $\log K_H$ increases. It may be that the variation of K_{H-L} has less effect as it occurs as logarithmic function.

(2) According to Braude¹⁰ on the addition of organic solvent to water, the tetrahedral lattice structure of water is gradually broken down and owing to the denser packing and smaller extent of hydrogen bonding

between water molecules, the stability of hydroxonium ion increases and the proton donating property of the medium falls. This may imply that the proton accepting property of the solvent increases. It is also said that the hydrogen bonded structure is less prevalent in pure ethanol in comparison to water and largely absent in pure acetone and pure dioxane. Gergely *et al.*⁴ have indicated that the dioxane molecules progressively break down the hydrogen bonded structure of the water whereas methanol can form hydrogen bonded associations with water. So it is expected that the extent of hydrogen bonding in alcohol water is greater than that in dioxane water or acetone water.

(3) *Protonation of the organic solvent*: When the proportion of organic solvent becomes sufficiently large in a water-organic solvent composition the proton solvation of the organic solvent molecules takes place. Braude¹¹ has reported that the basicities of the pure solvent molecules decreases in the following order :

Thus the proton solvation of pure acetone is minimum.

The effects (2) and (3) depend upon concentration of mixed aqueous media and they may be counteracting with respect to proton acceptance property of the media. Now the more a solvent accepts proton the more the ligand acid is dissociated and so the $^PK_1^H$ will tend to decrease.

The foregoing solvent effects influence the $^PK_1^H$ of ligand conjugate acid in the following manner :

(a) With increase of solvent dielectric constant $^PK_1^H$ of the ligand decreases and vice-versa.

(b) On decreasing the extent of hydrogen bonding in water by the organic solvent proton accepting property of water increases. So $^PK_1^H$ of ligand decreases.

(c) Increasing proton solvation by the organic solvent decreases the $^PK_1^H$ of ligand and vice-versa.

The sequence for $^PK_1^H$ values in the different solvents is almost the same as that of the dielectric constants of the solvents except acetone which is in the top place (slightly higher than dioxane). This may be explained by smaller proton solvation by acetone (c). Dioxane has to move to the second place possibly because it has large proton solvation capacity (c) and it decreases the hydrogen bonding in water (b).

K_{H-L} , the nonelectrostatic term in the equilibrium constant is also calculated from the variation of $\log ^PK_1^H$ vs $1/\epsilon$ (Fig. 1) with the help of equation 4. The curve is linear in all the solvents except dioxane. The $\log K_{H-L}$ values are shown in Table 2. Here again in the sequence for $\log K_{H-L}$ acetone comes first,

TABLE 2—VALUES OF 'a' AND $\log K_{H-L}$ CALCULATED FROM THE PLOTS OF $\log ^PK_1^H$ vs $1/\epsilon$ IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT WATER MIXTURES.

	Slope	Intercept	a	$\log K_{H-L}$
Methanol-water	56.45	8.32	4.24 A°	9.04
Ethanol-water	56.30	8.21	4.25 A°	8.92
Acetone-water	47.93	9.28	4.99 A°	9.62
Isopropanol-water	31.57	8.70	7.58 A°	9.62

Linear nature of the curves shows that the parameter 'a' more or less remains constant and $\log K_{H-L}$ varies only slightly in the range of composition studied. The values of 'a' are also computed (Table 2). Therefore in absence of quantitative values of the solvent effect (b) and (c) it can be said that $^PK_1^H$ in acetone water is highest as it has low proton solvation capacity, high $\log K_{H-L}$ values and rather low dielectric constant. Dioxane comes second because it has the lowest dielectric constant but greater proton solvation capacity (c) and greater capacity to decrease hydrogen bonding in water (b). Isopropanol, ethanol and methanol follow the sequence expected from their dielectric properties. Moreover the alcohols have higher proton solvation capacity than acetone.

Values of K_{H-L} and 'a' should be actually calculated with the help of thermodynamic constants. But it is expected that the given values calculated with the help of practical constants will not be much different.

In case of dioxane-water mixture (50% v/v to 85% v/v) the $\log ^PK_1^H$ increases with the increase of dioxane content of the mixture (Fig. 1). But there is some deviation from linearity. This is possibly due to larger deviation of $\log K_{H-L}$ and because both the effects (b) and (c) for dioxane lead to lowering of $^PK_1^H$.

Fig. 2. Variation of $\log ^PK_1^H$ vs mole fraction in various mixed aqueous solvents.

1. Dioxane-water ; 2. Isopropanol-water ; 3. Acetone-water ; 4. Ethanol-water and 5. Methanol-water.

$\log ^PK_1^H$ for NBPFA is also plotted against mole fractions for different solvents (Fig. 2). Here the variation is linear (except dioxane which shows slight deviation) and curve for acetone lies above those of others through a range of mole fractions. The sequence is the same as before i.e.,

Equilibrium constant β_1 and β_2 are tabulated in Table 1. They generally increase with decrease of dielectric constant or when the proportion of the organic solvent increases. In some cases in high proportions there is some deviation. In 75% v/v mixtures the sequence of $\log \beta_1$ is,

Isopropanol-water > dioxane-water = Ethanol-water = Methanol-water > Acetone-water

$\log \beta_2$ is,

Isopropanol-water \approx Ethanol-water > dioxane-water > methanol-water > acetone-water

Here acetone gets the last place. The order of the sequence is expected to be governed by the dielectric properties and proton solvation properties of the media. Acetone is already seen to have least proton solvating capacity among the solvents. So the position of acetone in the sequence is explained. Isopropanol possibly solvates proton strongly and also its dielectric constant is small.

The values of formation constant (β') are obtained from equilibrium constants ($\log \beta$) and $\log {}^P K_1^H$ values. Formation constants increase with the decrease of the dielectric constant of the solvent-water composition of any particular organic solvent^{3,4,6,8}. Fig. 3 shows the variation of $\log \beta_2'$ to be linear with respect to $1/\epsilon$. But when the proportion of organic solvent is high the rate of increase falls. Aqueous dioxane is an exception where slight deviation from linearity is observed.

In Fig. 4 $\log \beta_2'$ is plotted against mole fraction. Here also the variation is generally linear but some deviations are observed in solvent mixtures with high solvent proportions. The deviation can be explained by gradual replacement of water molecules in hydration sphere of metal ions by the organic solvent molecules at higher concentrations of the latter. This effect possibly increases the parameter 'a' in the expression (4). This may also influence the nonelectrostatic part of the interaction.

Fig. 3. Variation of $\log \beta_2'$ vs $1/\epsilon$ in various mixed aqueous solvents. The lower scale ($1/\epsilon$) is for dioxane-water.

1. Dioxane-water ; 2. Isopropanol-water ; 3. Acetone-water ; 4. Ethanol-water and 5. Methanol-water

Fig. 4. Variation of $\log \beta_2'$ vs mole fraction in various mixed aqueous solvents.

1. Dioxane-water ; 2. Isopropanol-water ; 3. Acetone-water ; 4. Ethanol-water and 5. Methanol-water

Comparison of the values of formation constants at 75% v/v show the following sequence in the solvent mixtures for both $\log \beta_1'$ and $\log \beta_2'$ values

Dioxane-water > Acetone-water > Isopropanol-water > Ethanol-water > Methanol-water

So the order is almost similar to the order of the dielectric constant only that acetone and isopropanol have exchanged places and it is also similar to the order of ${}^P K_1^H$ values except that acetone and dioxane have exchanged places. Such small differences are not unexpected considering the various solvent effects discussed before.

Comparison of the values of formation constants at 85% v/v reveal the following sequence

for $\log \beta_1'$:

Acetone-water > Dioxane-water > Isopropanol-water = Ethanol-water > Methanol-water

and for $\log \beta_2'$:

Acetone-water > Dioxane-water > Isopropanol-water > Ethanol-water > Methanol-water

We find the sequences to be similar to the sequence of ${}^P K_1^H$ in the solvents. Greater insight into these solvent effects which influence metal ligand complex formation could be achieved if such studies could be made in different similar volume proportions or similar mole fractions of all the solvent mixtures. This could hardly be done in the present research because of solubility difficulties.

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CHAUDHURY & KOLE : EFFECT OF DIFFERENT SOLVENT CHARACTERISTICS ON THE PROTON ETC.

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